

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

APOE (apolipoprotein E)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC

[348/ P02649](#)

Target Nominator

TREAT-AD

TREAT-AD Authors

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TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 4.68 (rank #3, 99.9th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target’s general relevance to Alzheimer’s Disease, and is the sum of the target’s Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 4.68 out of 5 (rank #3, 99.9th percentile). The individual score components include 2.85 of 3 for genetics, and 1.83 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of APOE protein is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. APOE is annotated to GO terms from 12 different biodomains, but primarily terms from the Lipid Metabolism,

Synapse, APP Metabolism, Vasculature, and Endolysosome biological domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer’s Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence

measures of expression. These data indicate that APOE is confidently expressed in astrocytes, microglia, and vascular and leptomeningeal cells (VLMC).

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

APOE is one of the strongest risk factors for late onset AD (LOAD) with a multitude of plausible biological effects in both neuronal and glial systems that could promote neurodegenerative processes, which are discussed in the section below. The goal of this TEP is to provide the scientific community with high quality resources that may help identify specific disease linked processes. The contents of this TEP include bioinformatic analysis, protein structural information and purified protein, and validated antibodies for APOE investigations. We hope these resources facilitate the efficiency and accuracy of future work in the field.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

The APOE gene is the most robust genetic risk factor for late-onset Alzheimer's disease (LOAD)(1,2) , and the strongest driver of genetic risk in AD outside of the familial Alzheimer's disease (FAD) autosomal dominant mutations in APP, PS1 and PS2 that give rise to early onset AD (EOAD)(3). There are three isoforms of the APOE gene, that differ at two amino acid positions (112 and 158), and are known as APOE2, APOE3 and APOE4(4). APOE2 is a protective allele with cysteines at both polymorphic positions (C112/C158), and is relatively rare, with an allele frequency around 8% (5). In contrast, APOE3 is the normative allele (with 78% allelic frequency(5)), being most prevalent in the population, and contains one cysteine and one arginine at the two polymorphic positions (C112/R158). APOE4 is the AD risk associated allele with arginine substitutions at both sites (R112/R158), and is also relatively rare, with an approximate 14% allelic frequency(5), which can increase AD risk by as much as 15-fold in homozygous allele carriers(4).

APOE plays a diversity of biological roles in the brain and peripheral systems, including binding and transport of cholesterol and phospholipids, loaded onto apolipoprotein by membrane bound ATP cassette lipid transporters ABCA and ABCG(4), which have also been identified by GWAS studies as associated with AD risk(6). Beyond lipids, APOE binds to receptors present in both microglia and neurons—namely TREM2 and LRP1(7–11). TREM2 is another known AD risk factor associated with altered microglial activation and amyloid phagocytosis(12–15), further highlighting the connection of the APOE associated processes with AD. APOE is composed of three different domains(4): the amino-terminal domain (1-167) contains the receptor interacting domain; a flexible hinge domain internal to the protein sequence, and the carboxy-terminal domain (206-299) that contains the lipid binding domain. While the polymorphic residues are completely contained within the amino-terminal receptor interaction domain, the amino- and carboxy-terminal domains fold back onto each other, allowing the two isoform determining residues to impact both domains(4). The APOE allele accelerates both the clinical manifestation of AD and the deposition of amyloid and tau pathology (16–18), suggesting a relatively central role in AD-linked biological processes.

Beyond amyloid and tau, APOE is also linked to concomitant non-AD pathology, such as Lewy body formation(18–22). APOE is expressed predominantly in the liver, outside of the brain, and facilitates

systemic cholesterol and phospholipid transport throughout the body. In the brain, APOE is expressed in astrocytes, microglia, and stressed neurons, in addition to vascular epithelial cells and the choroid plexus (4). In neurons, the different APOE isoforms may differentially regulate the expression level of APP, with APOE4 reported to drive the highest expression of APP, and result in elevated amyloid production, relative to APOE2 or APOE3 (23). Biologically, APOE is linked with numerous functions that may modify neurodegenerative processes(24–28), including cholesterol clearance from brain(29–32), regulation of innate immune response (33,34), and amyloid sedimentation and plaque formation (2,24–28). Consequently, the development of reliable tools to study various aspects of APOE biology may provide trenchant insight into AD linked biological processes.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for APOE. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies for APOE by immunoblot (Western blot), and immunoprecipitation. The cell line background was chosen based on the adequate expression of the target protein.

[YCharOS APOE Antibody Characterization Report](#)

Cell type specific expression

Using anti-human APOE antibody ab52607 as appears in the [YCharOS APOE Antibody Characterization Report](#), APOE expression was easily detected in human iPSC-derived astrocyte and microglia cell lysates but minimally detected in human iPSC-derived neuron cell lysates (Fig. 1). APOE was detectable in the conditioned media from WTC11 microglia, but minimally detected in conditioned media from other cell types. See **Additional Information** for cell line information, iPSC differentiation protocols, and Western blot conditions.

Figure 1. Expression of APOE in whole cell lysates (top) and media (bottom) across neurons (N), astrocytes (A), and microglia (M) derived from iPSC cell lines WTC11 (left) and F033K (right). Independent samples (n=2) were run in adjacent lanes.

Biological probe discovery:

- 1) **Immunodepletion of secreted protein in medium** : APOE was immunoprecipitated from media conditioned with WTC11-derived neurons. APOE was measured in eluate following immunoprecipitation by Western blot, and unbound APOE was detected in flowthrough by Western blot (Fig. 2). See **Additional Information** for experimental information on immunoprecipitation and Western blotting.

Figure 2. Immunoprecipitation (IP) of APOE using validated antibody ab52607 from WTC11 iPSC-derived astrocyte conditioned media. Western blot of eluted APOE (top) and unbound APOE in flowthrough (bottom) from media samples, $n=3$ technical replicates of single sample collection loaded in three adjacent lanes.

- 2) **Cell-based assays following immunodepletion**: To understand the impact of modulating APOE on cell function, we performed a small panel of assays on cells treated with anti-APOE antibody. iPSC-derived astrocytes were treated with anti-APOE before measuring IL-6 in conditioned media (Fig. 3). Treatment with anti-APOE did not significantly affect IL-6 levels in iPSC-astrocytes (ns). See **Additional Information** for experimental information.

Figure 3. Immunodepletion of APOE from iPSC derived astrocytes by treatment with anti-APOE antibody IL-6 levels in WTC11 astrocyte conditioned media when treated with anti-APOE antibody or IgG as measured by ELISA, $n=2$ independent experiments. ns= $p>0.05$.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of APOE in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

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ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Cell line information

The familial Alzheimer's disease (fAD) iPSC line (F033K) was previously generated from fibroblasts of a patient carrying the APP V717I (London) mutation(35). The well-characterized WTC11 iPSC line(36) and the F033K line were cultured in mTeSR1 medium (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 85850) on cell culture treated dishes coated with Geltrex LDEV-Free Reduced Growth Factor Basement Membrane Matrix (Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific; Cat. No. A1413201) diluted 1:100 in DMEM/F-12 (Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific; Cat. No. 11320033). Briefly, mTeSR1 was replaced every other day or every day once 50% confluent. When 80-90% confluent, cells were passaged, which entailed the following: aspirating media, washing with DPBS, incubating with ReLeSR (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0484) at RT for 3 minutes, aspirating ReLeSR, and incubating at 37°C for 10 minutes, resuspending in mTeSR1 supplemented with 10nM Y-27632 dihydrochloride ROCK inhibitor (Tocris; Cat. No. 125410), counting, and plating onto Matrigel-coated plates at desired number.

iPSC differentiation protocols

Astrocytes: Human iPSC-derived astrocytes (iAs) were generated as previously described(37). Briefly, iPSCs were plated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates and infected with rtTA, SOX9, and NFIB lentivirus. On Day 0, medium was replaced with fresh mTeSR-1 medium containing 2.5 µg/mL doxycycline. From Day 1-7, iAs were cultured in expansion medium (DMEM/F12, 10% FBS, 1% N2, 1.25 µg/mL puromycin, 200 µg/mL Hygromycin) and gradually transitioned to FGF medium (Neurobasal, 2% B27, 1% NEAA, 1% GlutaMax, 1% FBS, 8 ng/mL FGF, 5 ng/mL CNTF, 10 ng/mL BMP4, 200 µg/mL Hygromycin) by Day 7. On Day 7, iAs were dissociated using Accutase for 10 minutes, and replated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates in FGF medium. From Day 9, FGF medium was changed to Maturation medium (1:1 DMEM/F12 and Neurobasal, 1% N2, 1% Na Pyruvate, 10 µg/µL NAC, 10 µg/µL hbEGF, 10 ng/mL CNTF, 10 ng/mL BMP4, 500 µg/mL cAMP) and half of the medium was changed every 2 to 3 days.

Neurons: Human iPSC-derived neurons (iNs) were generated as previously described(38). Briefly, iPSCs were plated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates and infected with rtTA and NGN2 lentivirus. On Day 0, medium was replaced with fresh mTeSR-1 medium containing 2.5 µg/mL doxycycline. From Day 1-3, iNs were cultured in K2B medium (KO DMEM, 15% KSR, 1% NEAA, 0.1% BME, 1% GlutaMax, 2 µg/ml doxycycline) and gradually transitioned to N2B medium (DMEM/F12, 1% GlutaMax, 1.5% dextrose, 1% N2, 2 µg/ml doxycycline, 1 µg/mL puromycin) by Day 3. On Day 4, iNs were dissociated using Accutase for 5 minutes, and replated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates in NBM medium (Neurobasal, 1% GlutaMax, 1.5% dextrose, 0.5% NEAA, 2% B27, 10 ng/ml BDNF, 10 ng/ml GDNF, 10 ng/ml CNTF, 2 µg/ml doxycycline, 1µg/mL puromycin) and half of the medium was changed every 2 to 3 days.

Microglia: Human iPSC-derived microglia-like cells (iMGL) were generated by first differentiating human iPSCs into hematopoietic progenitor cells using the STEMdiff Hematopoietic Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 05310) per manufacturer's instructions. Then, hematopoietic progenitor cells were differentiated into microglia using the STEMdiff Microglia Differentiation Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0019) and matured using STEMdiff Microglia Maturation Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0020) following the manufacturer's instructions.

Western blotting

Media were collected and spun at 5000 X g for 10 min. The supernatants were stored at -80°C. For Western blotting, 1/3 volume of 4x Laemmli protein sample buffer (BioRad, 1610747) was added to culture media. After boiling at 98°C for 5 min. For cell lysate collection, after removing media, cells were washed with PBS twice and collected in PBS with a cell scraper. Cells were spun at 3000 rpm for 5 min, and the supernatants were discarded. Cells were lysed in NP-40 buffer (1% nonidet P-40, 20 mM Tris (PH 7.4), 137 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol) with protease inhibitor (Sigma, P8340) and phosphatase inhibitor (Sigma, P5726 and P0044). 1/3 volume of 4x Laemmli protein sample buffer (BioRad, #1610747) was added to lysate and samples were boiled at 98°C for 5 min. For Western blotting, cell culture media and lysates were separated on 10% Tris-glycine SDS-polyacrylamide gels. Proteins were transferred to 0.2 µm nitrocellulose membrane (BioRad, 1620112). The membrane was blocked with 5% non-fat milk for 1 hr and incubated with APOE antibody (Abcam, ab52607) with 1:1000 dilution in TBST containing 3% BSA at 4°C overnight with gentle rocking. The membrane was washed with TBST for 10 mins three times and then incubated with the secondary antibody (Jackson ImmunoResearch Laboratories, #111-035-003) at 1:5000 at room temperature for 1 hr. After washing with TBST for 10 mins three times, images were taken with the ChemiDoc Imaging System (BioRad, 12003153).

Immunoprecipitation

Cell culture media were collected as described above for Western blotting. APOE antibody (Abcam, ab52607) was added to media (0.75 µg/ml) and incubated at 4°C overnight with gentle rocking. Protein A/G beads (Santa Cruz, sc-2003) were prewashed with PBS twice and resuspended with lysis buffer after final wash. 30 µl slurry of resuspended beads were added to media which were incubated with the antibody. After two hours incubation at 4°C, beads were pelleted by centrifugation at 3,000 rpm (approximately 1,000xg) for 30 seconds at 4°C. The supernatants were collected to serve as flowthrough. Beads were washed with PBS 3 times. 30-50 ul 2x Laemmli sample buffer (BioRad, 1610737) was added to the beads pellet. After boiling for 5 minutes, samples can be stored at -20°C for Western blotting.

Immunodepletion in cell media

APOE antibody (Abcam, ab52607) was added to media (0.75 µg/ml) with iPSC derived cells. The cells were further cultured for 3 days at 37°C in humidified conditions with 5% CO₂. Cell culture media were collected as described above for Western blotting. Prewashed protein A/G beads were added to media and incubated at 4°C for two hours. The following steps are the same as immunoprecipitation for cell media described above.

Measurement of IL-6

The enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kit specific for human IL-6 (R&D Systems: #QK206) was used to quantify IL-6 according to the manufacturer's instructions. Results were expressed as percentages of the isotype control. The means from duplicate measurements are presented.

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